

CONTROLLING THE REACTION RATE OF ANIONIC POLYAMIDE-6 FOR VACUUM INFUSION OF COMPOSITE WIND TURBINE BLADES

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SUMMARY: In order to manufacture large thermoplastic composite wind turbine blades with an otherwise fast reacting anionic polyamide-6 casting resin, the reaction rate has to be decreased to accommodate for the long mould filling times associated with the vacuum infusion process. This paper discusses three potential methods to accomplish this. The first method, reduction of the amount of initiator in the resin formulation, is not an option due to partial deactivation caused by impurities on the fiber surface. The second method, reduction of the polymerization temperature, is not very effective and, more importantly, significantly influences the final polymer properties. The choice of a suitable activator-initiator combination, the third method, is by far the most effective. Using a difunctional carbamoylcaprolactam activator in combination with a caprolactam magnesium bromide initiator results in a two-step reaction mechanism. In the initial slow step infusion of the fibers can take place, whereas in the subsequent faster step the final curing takes place leading to demolding.

KEYWORDS: Thermoplastic composites, vacuum infusion, resin formulation, reaction rate.

INTRODUCTION

Following international agreements on reducing CO₂-emission, the Dutch government has formulated the ambitious target to have a 6,000 Megawatt wind power park installed offshore in 2020. A pilot program called PHD@SEA is initiated by the WE@SEA foundation (Wind Energy at Sea [1]), which reflects the combined effort of public and private interest towards realizing this target. In the next decades, more than 1,000 turbines need to be installed in the North Sea. The two main requirements formulated by WE@SEA for the 3,000 blades to be constructed are durability and sustainability.

In that respect, a process for manufacturing large thermoplastic composite (TPC) blades is being developed at Delft University of Technology. Due to the higher toughness of the matrix, TPCs potentially offer a higher resistance to fatigue than their thermoset-based counterparts that are currently used, such as fiber-reinforced epoxies and vinylesters. In addition, TPCs can be remolded upon melting, enabling re-use of the blade material. In order to produce blades with lengths in excess of 50 meter, the currently most widely applied manufacturing process for turbine blades, vacuum infusion, is the preferred choice. This process utilizes a low

viscosity resin that is injected into a mould with pre-placed dry fibers, followed by a curing step. Since the viscosity of thermoplastic polymer melts is too high, reactive processing is required: a low viscosity monomer melt is injected between the fibers, together with an activating system, if required, followed by *in situ* polymerization of the monomer to form a linear polymer with a sufficiently high molecular weight.

This article discusses the use of anionic polyamide-6 (APA-6) for the manufacturing of large composite structures through vacuum infusion. The anionic ring opening polymerization of caprolactam into high molecular weight polyamide-6 (PA-6) is a catalyzed reaction performed at 130-170 °C [2]. Final conversions can be obtained in 3 to 60 minutes, depending on the type and amount of activator and initiator added. Since polymerization takes place below the polymer melting and crystallization point, polymerization and crystallization take place simultaneously, resulting in highly crystalline (40-50% [3]) solid PA-6.

Since the 1970's, this resin system has been extensively used for (monomer) casting of stock-shapes. This process is characterized by short mould filling times, which allows the use of fast reacting resin formulations. In order to accommodate the longer mould filling times encountered in vacuum infusion, especially when manufacturing large components such as turbine blades, the reaction rate has to be reduced significantly, which is discussed in this paper.

MATERIALS AND PROCESSING METHODS

Anionic polymerization grade caprolactam (AP-Caprolactam, see Fig. 1) supplied by DSM Fiber Intermediates, The Netherlands, was used in this study due to its low moisture content (<100 ppm). The monomer was stored at 50 °C under atmospheric conditions to keep it dry without causing the monomer flakes to fuse together due to sublimation and recrystallization. Two types of activators were used in this study, as shown in Fig. 1. The first is monofunctional N-acetylcaprolactam (100%, "Activator0", Brüggemann Chemical, Germany) and the second is difunctional hexamethylene-1,6-dicarbamoylcaprolactam (2 mol/kg concentration in caprolactam, "Bruggolen C20", Brüggemann Chemical, Germany). The former was stored as liquid in glass jars, whereas the latter was stored as granules in sealed polyethylene lined aluminum drums. Sodium caprolactamate (1 mol/kg concentration in caprolactam, "Bruggolen C10", Brüggemann Chemical, Germany) and caprolactam magnesium bromide (1.4 mol/kg concentration in caprolactam, "Bruggolen C1", Brüggemann Chemical, Germany) were used as initiator, see Fig. 1. Both were stored as flakes in sealed polyethylene lined aluminum drums.

Fig. 1: Structures of materials used in this study: (a) caprolactam, (b) N-acetylcaprolactam, (c) hexamethylene-1,6-dicarbamoylcaprolactam, (d) sodium caprolactamate, and (e) caprolactam magnesium bromide.

A special designed lab-scale mixing unit (Mini Mixing Unit "MMU-TU Delft", Bronk Industrial b.v., The Netherlands) was used to prepare two liquid material formulations at 110 °C under a nitrogen atmosphere: a monomer/activator-mixture in tank A and a monomer/initiator-mixture in tank B, see Fig. 2. After degassing both tanks (15 minutes at

100 mbar), the two material feeds were dispensed (1:1 ratio) and mixed by using a static mixer.

Fig. 2: Infusion equipment. Left: Mini Mixing Unit “MMU-TU Delft”, right: Stainless Steel infusion mould.

Test tubes (Schott-Fiolax, 20 x 150 mm) placed in a heated oil bath were used as a casting mould to manufacture neat APA-6 samples. Rubber stoppers were used to prevent uptake of moisture and oxygen from air. A stainless Steel infusion mould, see Fig. 2, was used together with a 3 mm thick stainless Steel cover plate to manufacture neat APA-6 plates (170 x 200 x 2 mm). Homogeneous heating of the mould was obtained by placing it in a horizontally placed hot flat platen press. Infusion from bottom to top is necessary to prevent entrapment of air and was accomplished by connecting a vacuum pump to the resin outlet. A pressure control system ensured that infusion and polymerization always took place at 500 mbar (actual pressure in the mould cavity).

ANALYSIS METHODS

The degree of conversion (X) of cast APA-6 samples was determined according to the method presented in [4]. To obtain conversion-time relations, polymerization was terminated at various stages by quenching the test tubes containing the sample in ice water.

The viscosity average molar mass (M_v) was determined by dilute solution viscometry in a Micro-Ubbelohde Capillary II. Aqueous H_2SO_4 (40%) was used as solvent. A single-point measurement at a concentration of 0.5 g/dl was used to obtain an approximation of M_v for each sample according to the method discussed in [5].

A Perkin Elmer Differential Scanning Calorimeter (DSC-7) was used to measure the degree of crystallinity (X_c) and melting point (T_m) of the various samples of approximately 5 mg, which were dried overnight at 50°C in a vacuum oven. During testing, each sample was first held for 2 minutes at 25 °C before being heated to 230 °C at 10 °C/min. X_c was calculated according to Eq. 1.

$$X_c = \frac{\Delta H_m}{\Delta H_{100}} \cdot 100\% \quad (1)$$

In which ΔH_{100} is the melting enthalpy of fully crystalline PA-6: $\Delta H_{100} = 190$ J/g [6].

Tensile tests were performed on a Zwick 1455 universal testing machine according to ISO 527-2. Dog bone shaped specimen (type 1b, 5 of each sample) were dried prior to testing at 50 °C and 50 mbar for at least 85 hours to obtain dry as molded (DAM) values.

POLYMERIZATION RATE

The anionic polymerization of caprolactam into polyamide-6, see Fig. 3, basically consists of three steps: (i) dissociation of the initiator (in most cases a metal caprolactamate) or “anion formation”, (ii) “complex formation” between the initiator and the activator (however, not all combinations of activator and initiator are able to do so), and (iii) “polymerization” through the anions during which an anion is regenerated after every monomer addition [7].

Fig. 3: Anionic polymerization of ϵ -caprolactam into polyamide-6, using hexamethylene-1,6-dicarbamoylcaprolactam as activator and caprolactam magnesium bromide as initiator.

The reaction rate predominantly depends on the combination of activator and initiator. The difference in activity of the various activator-initiator combinations is explained by the fact that a solution of a metal caprolactamate in caprolactam is hardly dissociated. The dissociation constant at 150 °C for sodium caprolactamate, for example, is only $6.7 \cdot 10^{-5}$ mole/l and as a result hardly any anions are generated [8]. The rate of dissociation, and therefore the activity of the initiator, decreases with increasing size of the cation due to a decreasing ionization potential and restricted mobility [8]. An alternative way to generate anions is through complex formation between the activator and the cation of the initiator [11-13]. Whether or not a complex can be formed depends on both the geometry and the electric forces of the activator and the metal cation of the initiator. In addition, the stronger the complex that can be formed, the higher the rate at which anions are generated and consequently the higher the reaction rate. When no complex can be formed, anions are only generated in small amounts due to dissociation, hence resulting in a low reaction rate.

Fig. 4: Conversion-time relations for four common activator-initiator combinations (0.6 mol% activator, 0.6 mol% initiator) polymerized at 150 °C.

Fig. 4 shows the conversion in time for four common activator-initiator combinations (0.6 mol% activator, 0.6mol% initiator) polymerized at 150 °C. The accompanying table shows whether or not a complex is formed. It can be seen that for the two combinations that lead to complex formation, the polymerization is fastest and that the conversion increases exponentially in time. In case no complex is formed, polymerization is slower and the conversion increase is more linear in time. In the case of the hexamethylene-1,6-dicarbamoylcaprolactam activator in combination with the magnesiumbromide caprolactamate initiator (C20-C1) initially no complex is formed, which explains the slow conversion increase at the beginning of the reaction. However, after a single monomer addition, the carbamoylcaprolactam group is replaced by an acetylcaprolactam group, which is the same reactive group as the one of Activator0. Since this group is able to form a complex with the C1 initiator, the reaction rate increases rapidly after a while.

POLYMERIZATION RATE VS PROCESSING METHOD

Originally APA-6 was developed for the monomer casting process. In a casting process, the reactive mixture is poured into a heated mould after which polymerization takes place. Due to the water-like viscosity of the monomer and the absence of low permeable fiber reinforcement, using gravitational forces alone to fill the mould already leads to very short mould-filling times. To decrease product cycle time, a fast-reacting formulation, such as “C20-C10” is often used, see Figure 4.

Due to the low permeability of the fiber preform, the required mould filling times required for vacuum infusion are much longer. In order to manufacture large composite products like wind turbine blades, a slower reacting formulation is required compared to the ones traditionally used for casting. The two-step reaction mechanism of the “C20-C1” combination seems ideal for this purpose. In the initial slow step infusion of the fibers can take place, whereas in the subsequent faster step the final curing occurs. It has been determined experimentally that a 10% conversion relates to a viscosity of 1 Pa·s, the generally accepted maximum viscosity at which infusion of a fiber perform is still possible.

Fig. 5: Processing window for APA-6 (0.6 mol% C20 and 1.2 mol% C1).
Reproduced from [9].

A processing window for the “C20-C1” is given for various polymerization temperatures in Fig. 5. Note that the amount of initiator has been increased up to 1.2 mol%, which is necessary to compensate for the partial deactivation of the initiator due to contact with impurities on the fiber surface such as sizings and water [10, 11]. Consequently, slowing down the reaction by reducing the amount of initiator as is done with casting is not an option in the case of vacuum infusion of fiber reinforced APA-6. Fig. 5 seems to indicate that besides the activator-catalyst combination also a reduction in polymerization temperature can

be used to increase the infusion window. However, besides the fact that a drop in polymerization temperature is not as effective as changing the activator-initiator combination, it also strongly influences the crystallization kinetics, which can have a detrimental effect on the polymer properties as will be discussed below.

POLYMER PROPERTIES

The properties of anionic PA-6 polymerized at various temperatures using 0.6 mol% C20 and 1.2 Mol% C1 are shown in Table 1. The increasing temperature decreases the degree of crystallinity, but results in a significant increase in molecular weight, which indicates the occurrence of branching caused by the difunctional nature of the activator as is found in literature [12]. From the fact that with increasing temperature the Young's modulus and the tensile stress increase the conclusion can be drawn that the degree of crystallinity plays a more dominant role on the mechanical properties than the molecular weight. The slight reduction in mechanical properties at 140 °C compared to 150 °C despite the increase in crystallinity might be attributed to the reduction in final conversion. It is a known fact that at polymerization temperatures below 140 °C the crystallization rate becomes so high that reactive groups can become trapped inside growing crystals before they can polymerize. The resulting low conversions lead to a cheese-like soft material rather than a rigid polymer [8]. The slight reduction in obtained conversion and mechanical properties at 140 °C may be due to the onset of this phenomenon and it can indeed be concluded that a further reduction of temperature to decrease the polymerization rate is not an option.

Table 1. APA-6 properties for various polymerization temperatures (0.6 mol% C20 and 1.2 mol% C1).

Polymerisation temperature [°C]	Crystallinity [%]	Mv -	Young's modulus [GPa]	Yield stress [MPa]	Yield Strain [%]	Final degree of conversion [%]
140	42.2	44,000	3.7	64.0	2.7	97.0
150	38.7	47,000	3.8	76.0	3.5	97.5
160	34.3	62,000	3.2	64.0	3.4	97.2
170	33.2	92,000	2.7	56.0	3.7	96.9

CONCLUSIONS

In order to manufacture large thermoplastic composite wind turbine blades with an otherwise fast reacting anionic polyamide-6 casting resin, the reaction rate has to be decreased to accommodate for the long mould filling times associated with the vacuum infusion process. This paper discusses three potential methods to accomplish this. The first method, reduction of the amount of initiator in the resin formulation, is not an option due to partial deactivation caused by impurities on the fiber surface. The second method, reduction of the polymerization temperature, is not very effective and, more importantly, significantly influences the final polymer properties. The choice of a suitable activator-initiator combination, the third method, is by far the most effective. Using a difunctional carbamoylcaprolactam activator in combination with a caprolactam magnesium bromide initiator results in a two-step reaction mechanism. In the initial slow step infusion of the fibers can take place, whereas in the subsequent faster step the final curing takes. Additionally, it was shown that for this formulation, an increase in polymerization temperature results in a higher degree of cross-linking and a lower degree of crystallinity. As with all semi-crystalline polymers, the Young's modulus and the tensile strength increase with increasing degree of crystallinity, whereas the elongation at break decreases.

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